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A NOVEL CO₂ ACTIVATION AT ROOM TEMPERATURE TO PREPARE AN ENGINEERED LANTHANUM-BASED ADSORBENT FOR A SUSTAINABLE ARSENIC REMOVAL FROM WATER

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Abstract:	<p>A novel activation route for carbon-based adsorbents functionalized with lanthanum and its application for arsenic adsorption was proposed. This procedure is based on carbon dioxide activation at room temperature thus drastically reducing energy consumption and adsorbent costs. A comparison of this novel activation approach with respect to the conventional thermal activation at 800 °C under N₂ atmosphere was performed on biochar from avocado seeds and functionalized with lanthanum. Results showed that the arsenic adsorption properties of the lanthanum-functionalized adsorbent activated with CO₂ at room temperature were higher up to 62% than those activated with N₂ at 800 °C. The carbonation of lanthanum oxygenated functionalities on the adsorbent surface favored the ligand exchange and surface complexation interactions during the arsenic adsorption. Arsenic adsorption using this engineered lanthanum-based adsorbent was endothermic and transitioned from a multi-molecular process at 25 °C to a multi-anchorage process at 30 °C. The estimated arsenic adsorption capacities at saturation for these novel adsorbents were 15 – 20 mg/g at 25 – 40 °C, respectively.</p>

Highlights

- An engineered lanthanum adsorbent was prepared for arsenic adsorption
- Carbon dioxide activation at room temperature is a green route to improve the arsenic adsorption
- Carbonation of lanthanum oxygenated functionalities contributed to the arsenic removal

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4 **A NOVEL CO₂ ACTIVATION AT ROOM TEMPERATURE TO PREPARE AN**
5 **ENGINEERED LANTHANUM-BASED ADSORBENT FOR A SUSTAINABLE ARSENIC**
6 **REMOVAL FROM WATER**
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22 **ABSTRACT**

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24 A novel activation route for the preparation of carbon-based adsorbents functionalized with
25 lanthanum and their application for arsenic adsorption was proposed. This procedure is based on
26 carbon dioxide activation at room temperature, which could allow to reduce the energy consumption
27 and adsorbent cost. A comparison of this novel activation approach with respect to the conventional
28 thermal activation at 800 °C under N₂ atmosphere was performed on biochar from avocado seeds and
29 functionalized with lanthanum. Results showed that the arsenic adsorption properties of the
30 lanthanum-functionalized adsorbent activated with CO₂ at room temperature were higher up to 62%
31 than those activated with N₂ at 800 °C. The carbonation of lanthanum oxygenated functionalities on
32 the adsorbent surface favored the ligand exchange and surface complexation interactions during the
33 arsenic adsorption. Arsenic adsorption using this engineered lanthanum-based adsorbent was
34 endothermic and transited from a multi-molecular process at 25 °C to a multi-anchorage process at
35 30 °C. The estimated arsenic adsorption capacities at saturation for these novel adsorbents were 15 –
36 20 mg/g at 25 – 40 °C, respectively.
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46 **Keywords:** Arsenic, Carbon dioxide activation, Lanthanum functionalization, Water treatment.
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1. INTRODUCTION

The preparation of tailored adsorbents for the effective removal of water pollutants is a challenge of particular interest especially for geogenic elements highly toxic like arsenic (Zhang et al., 2007; Davidescu et al., 2011; Ciopec et al., 2013; Negrea et al., 2014; Islam et al., 2021; Lv et al., 2021). This metalloid is cataloged as a priority groundwater pollutant and is hazardous for human beings even at very low concentrations (Kumar et al., 2020). Different studies have shown that traditional adsorbents (e.g., activated carbons, zeolites or clays) require an appropriate functionalization to adapt their surface chemistry and improve the adsorption properties for the arsenic adsorption from aqueous solutions (Zhang et al., 2007; Nguyen et al., 2019; Soni and Shukla, 2019; Aryee et al., 2021; Islam et al., 2021; Zoroufchi et al., 2021; Wen et al., 2021). In this context, it is convenient to remark that the cost-effectiveness tradeoff of adsorption process is fundamental for its large-scale application in arsenic depollution of groundwater especially in low-income countries. The process scale-up feasibility is mainly determined by the adsorption capacity of the adsorbent used as separation medium and, consequently, it is the main factor that could constrain the implementation in water purification. Surface functionalization procedures based on multivalent species (e.g., iron, aluminum, cesium) have proved to be effective to enhance the adsorption properties of several materials employed in the arsenic removal with the goal of contributing to reduce the costs of groundwater treatment (Fierro et al., 2009; Hu et al., 2015; Cortés-Arriagada and Toro-Labbé, 2016; Hu et al., 2016; Alijani and Shariatinia, 2017; Yu et al., 2017; Yu et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2018; Lin et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2019a; Li et al., 2020; Tan et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020; Al-Gaashani et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2021; Kouotou et al., 2022). Lanthanum has found remarkable properties in adsorbing arsenic and other inorganic and organic compounds (e.g., dyes, phosphates, fluoride, heavy metals) (Di et al., 2006; Deng and Yu, 2012; Sun et al., 2012; Tao et al., 2012; Tang et al., 2014; Mendoza-Castillo et al., 2016; Kalidindi et al., 2017; Zúñiga-Muro et al., 2017; Jeon et al., 2018; Lingamdinne et al., 2019). This metal is classed as a non-toxic because it does not participate in the biochemical processes of human beings as well as an environmentally friendly element with different physicochemical characteristics including antimicrobial properties (Liu et al., 2013; Manikandan et al., 2017; Prabhu et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2022). A number of lanthanum-based adsorbents has been prepared and tested in water purification (Tokunaga et al., 1997; Haron et al., 2001; Kamble et al., 2007; Liu et al., 2013; Kuroki et al., 2014; Velazquez-Jimenez et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2015; Jais et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2016; Prabhu et al., 2018; Lingamdinne et al., 2019; Tang et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2019; Jia et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020; Merodio-Morales et al., 2020; Sahu et al., 2020; Tan et al., 2020). For example, Liu et al. (2013) used activated carbon fibers to deposit lanthanum and iron for phosphate adsorption. Also, different adsorbents were obtained by the

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4 pyrolysis of oak sawdust with LaCl_3 at different temperatures where these materials were assessed in
5 the adsorption of ammonium, nitrates and phosphates (Wang et al., 2015). A carbon-based adsorbent
6 obtained from the palm shell waste was magnetized and coated with lanthanum to carry out a
7 comparative study to remove arsenate (Jais et al., 2016). Wang et al. (2016) synthesized a lanthanum-
8 based adsorbent using oak chips for phosphate adsorption. TiO_2 -La composite was evaluated for the
9 removal of arsenic and fluoride (Yan et al., 2017). On the other hand, Liao et al. (2018) prepared a
10 magnetic pineapple adsorbent with different $\text{La}(\text{OH})_3$ contents to reduce the concentration of
11 phosphates in water. Lingamdinne et al. (2019) synthesized a graphene oxide-lanthanum
12 nanocomposite for arsenic removal, while Wu et al. (2019b) studied the phosphate adsorption using
13 lanthanum diatomite. Jia et al. (2020), Sahu et al. (2020) and Jin et al. (2021) have also reported the
14 preparation of lanthanum-based adsorbents for the phosphate and fluoride removal from aqueous
15 solutions.
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17 Overall, the preparation and functionalization of adsorbents with lanthanum include
18 thermochemical routes that can be performed at 200 – 1000 °C with a variety of operating conditions
19 (e.g., dwell times and lanthanum concentrations) depending on the nature of feedstock and activation
20 procedures (Wang et al., 2015; Jais et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2019; Jia et al., 2020;
21 Jiang et al., 2020; Merodio-Morales et al., 2020). Thermal treatments involved in the adsorbent
22 synthesis (e.g., pyrolysis, carbonization and activation) are responsible of the energy consumption
23 that consequently increases the production cost of these materials. For illustration, it has been
24 estimated that the energy consumption to obtain activated carbons from different biomass can range
25 from 43 to 277 MJ/kg where the activation temperature has a significant impact on this energy
26 requirement (Liao et al., 2020). These calculations also indicated that around 30% of energy
27 consumption of activated carbon production can be related to the activation stage (Liao et al., 2020).
28 Based on the fact that the current industry demand of adsorbents for water treatment is estimated
29 around ~866 kiloton (Mordor Intelligence, 2021), it is necessary to explore new alternatives to reduce
30 the energy costs associated with the preparation routes and to develop sustainable supply chains of
31 novel materials for groundwater treatment.
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33 This manuscript reports a new activation route using CO_2 at room temperature to synthesize an
34 engineered lanthanum-based adsorbent for the arsenic removal from aqueous solution. The activation
35 of lanthanum-functionalized adsorbents using N_2 at 800 °C versus CO_2 at room temperature was
36 analyzed and compared. Results showed that the arsenic adsorption properties of this adsorbent can
37 be tailored using CO_2 at room temperature thus offering the possibility of reducing the energy
38 consumption (and its corresponding cost) involved in the activation stage. Finally, a detailed
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4 interpretation of the surface chemistry of this engineered adsorbent and its arsenic adsorption
5 mechanism was carried out.
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8 9 **2. METHODOLOGY**

10 *2.1 Preparation of an engineered lanthanum-functionalized char and its activation using N₂ and* 11 *CO₂* 12 13

14 A comparative study of different routes for the lanthanum functionalization and activation of a
15 carbon-based material was performed. A biochar obtained from avocado seeds from *Persea*
16 *Americana* was used for the functionalization tests. This lignocellulosic biomass is a potential
17 renewable feedstock that is widely generated in Mexico and can be utilized as an alternative precursor
18 for the carbon-based adsorbent production at industrial scale (di Bitonto et al., 2021). First, a char
19 was obtained from the pyrolysis of *Persea americana* seeds. Then, this precursor was cleaned with
20 hot deionized water, dried, grounded and sieved to obtain a mean particle sized of 0.67 mm. 30 g of
21 this biomass were packed in a quartz tube and pyrolyzed at 800 °C for 2 h in a Carbolite Eurotherm
22 tubular furnace. These pyrolysis conditions were determined from preliminary experiments (not
23 reported for the sake of brevity). Biomass pyrolysis was carried out with a heating rate of 10 °C/min
24 under N₂ flow of 100 mL/min. This carbon-based adsorbent was functionalized with lanthanum
25 solution using two different ratios (i.e., 5 and 10% w/w) where these solutions were prepared with
26 La(NO₃)₃•6H₂O salt and deionized water. The mixture of adsorbent and lanthanum solution was
27 stirred in a rotary evaporator at 120 rpm and 25 °C for 1 h. Then, NaOH 1.5 M solution was added
28 dropwise until a lanthanum hydroxide precipitate was obtained. After the precipitation, the sample
29 was kept on the rotary evaporator at 70 °C and the system was stirred at 120 rpm for 1 h, the
30 suspension was filtered and the final solid (i.e., lanthanum-functionalized adsorbent) was washed
31 with deionized water to remove the reagent excess and finally dried for 24 h. Two alternatives for the
32 activation of lanthanum-functionalized chars were analyzed: a) activation at 25 °C for 2 h under CO₂
33 flow and b) activation at 800 °C for 2 h under N₂ flow. 100 mL/min of either CO₂ or N₂ was employed
34 in this activation stage. The final adsorbents were washed with deionized water to remove the residual
35 chemicals from functionalization and activation, and finally dried for 24 h. These adsorbents were
36 labeled as C-LaX and N-LaX where C and N denotes the activation atmosphere (i.e., C: CO₂ and N:
37 N₂) and X represents the lanthanum ratio used in the adsorbent functionalization (i.e., 5 and 10%
38 w/w).
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57 *2.2 Arsenic adsorption using the engineered lanthanum-functionalized adsorbents* 58 59 60 61 62 63 64 65

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4 Arsenic adsorption properties of the lanthanum-functionalized materials were assessed with batch
5 adsorbers operated at 25, 30 and 40 °C, pH 7 and 8 for 24 h of contact time and using an arsenic
6 solution concentration of 200 mg/L. The best samples (C-La10 and N-La10) were used to quantify
7 the kinetics and isotherms of arsenic adsorption. Kinetic studies were done at 30 °C, pH 7, contact
8 time of 0.5 – 24 h and using initial arsenic concentrations of 50, 100 and 200 mg/L. Arsenic adsorption
9 isotherms were obtained at 25, 30 and 40 °C, pH 7, 24 h of equilibrium time and initial concentrations
10 from 20 to 200 mg/L. The agitation speed and adsorbent-adsorbate ratio were 120 rpm and 2 g/L,
11 respectively, for all the adsorption experiments. Standard commercial arsenic solutions were utilized
12 in adsorption tests. Speciation diagram of arsenic indicated that HAsO_4^{2-} and H_2AsO_4^- were the main
13 species dissolved in the aqueous solution at tested pH. Arsenic concentrations of the adsorption
14 experiments were determined with atomic adsorption via a Thermo Scientific iCE3000 spectrometer.
15 All experiments were done in triplicate until to obtain a reproducibility $\leq 5\%$ and the mean value of
16 these replicates were reported and analyzed. Arsenic adsorption capacities (q_{As} , mg/g) were estimated
17 from the material balance of a batch adsorber

$$q_{As,t} = \frac{(C_{As,ini} - C_{As,t})V_{As}}{m_{LaX}} \quad (1)$$

18 where $C_{As,ini}$ and $C_{As,t}$ are the initial and final arsenic concentrations (mg/L) from the adsorption
19 experiment and V_{As}/m_{LaX} is the adsorbate-adsorbent ratio (L/g), respectively.

20 The pseudo-second order kinetic model (Ho and McKay, 1999) was employed to calculate the
21 arsenic adsorption rate constants (k_2 , g/mg·h) using the next expression

$$q_{As,t} = \frac{q_{As,eq}^2 k_2 t}{1 + q_{As,eq} k_2 t} \quad (2)$$

22 where $q_{As,eq}$ is the estimated arsenic adsorption capacity (mg/g) and t is the adsorption time (h).

23 The changes of enthalpy (ΔH° , kJ/mol), entropy (ΔS° , kJ/mol K) and Gibbs free energy (ΔG° ,
24 kJ/mol) for the arsenic adsorption were estimated via the van't Hoff approach (Lima et al., 2020)
25 where the adsorption equilibrium constants were obtained using the methodology reported by Tran
26 et al. (2017).

27 A monolayer adsorption model based on statistical physics theory was applied to calculate the
28 steric parameters and interaction energy for the arsenic adsorption on lanthanum-functionalized
29 adsorbents. This model assumed that one binding site was responsible of the adsorption of arsenic
30 species from the aqueous solution thus forming an adsorbate monolayer on the adsorbent surface. It
31 was also considered that the lanthanum functionalities were the main binding sites on these materials
32 and they could adsorb a variable number of arsenic species. It is convenient to remark that lanthanum
33 has a great affinity for anions, makes stable compounds with them and has the possibility of

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4 interacting simultaneously with several arsenic anions due to its valence (Wang et al., 2016;
5 Lingamdinne et al., 2019). Therefore, this adsorption model is given by (Amrhar et al., 2021)
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$$7 \quad q_{As} = \frac{n_{As} D_{LaX}}{1 + \left(\frac{C_{1/2}}{C_e}\right)^{n_{As}}} \quad (3)$$

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11 where q_{As} is the arsenic adsorption capacity (mg/g), n_{As} represents the number of arsenic ions adsorbed
12 per lanthanum functionalities of tested adsorbents, D_{LaX} is the density of these functional groups that
13 were involved in the arsenic adsorption (mg/g) and $C_{1/2}$ and C_e are the arsenic concentration at half-
14 saturation and at equilibrium (mg/L), respectively. Interaction energy for arsenic – lanthanum
15 functionalities (ΔE_{As-LaX} , kJ/mol) was calculated with the next equation
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$$19 \quad \Delta E_{As-LaX} = RT \ln \left(\frac{S_{As}}{C_{1/2}} \right) \quad (4)$$

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21 where R is the universal gas constant (kJ/mol·K) and S_{As} is the arsenic solubility in water (mg/L). A
22 nonlinear regression was performed using a stochastic optimization method to globally minimize the
23 corresponding objective function for the kinetic and equilibrium data.
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30 *2.3 Physicochemical properties and surface chemistry characterization of engineered lanthanum-* 31 *functionalized adsorbents*

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33 Samples of tested adsorbents were characterized with different analytical techniques. The pH at
34 point of zero charge (pHpzc) was determined mixing the adsorbent with 0.1 M NaCl solutions that
35 were adjusted to different initial pH values by adding either HCl or NaOH, and using an adsorbent-
36 electrolyte ratio of 3 g/L. The suspensions containing adsorbent samples were stirred at 25 °C for 48
37 h and the final pH was recorded. The value of pHpzc was identified following the data plotting
38 approach reported in the literature (Kalavathy and Miranda, 2010; Vieira et al., 2010). The elemental
39 composition of tested adsorbents was determined with an Epsilon 4 X-ray fluorescence (XRF)
40 spectrometer (Malvern-Panalytical) in air atmosphere with an Ag anode at 50 kV and 3 mA. The
41 powder samples were placed into plastic capsules using a 3.6 micron Mylar window prior their
42 analysis. Omnian software was used for data processing where the predominant elements were
43 detected. The crystalline adsorbent structure was studied via X-ray diffraction (XRD) with an
44 Empyrean Diffractometer (Malvern-Panalytical) in the range of 10 to 70 °2θ at 45 kV and 40 mA at
45 room temperature using the Bragg-Brentano geometry, CuKα1 radiation ($\lambda=1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) and a
46 PIXcel1D-Medipix3 detector. All samples were analyzed at a scanning speed of 96.39 s with a step
47 size of 0.026 °2θ. HighScore Plus software and PDF2 database were utilized to interpret the
48 diffraction patterns. The functional groups from the surface of lanthanum-based adsorbents were
49 identified via Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). Powdered samples of these adsorbents
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4 were mixed with FTIR-grade KBr, and the mixtures were grounded and pressed to obtain translucent
5 tablets. These tablets were mounted in a quartz FTIR cell and scanned 32 times at room temperature
6 in the transmittance mode over the range of 4000 - 400 cm^{-1} (4 cm^{-1} resolution) with a Thermo
7 Scientific Infrared Spectrometer (Nicolet iS10). The surface chemical composition of selected
8 adsorbent sample was also analyzed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). Survey and high-
9 resolution (O1s, La3d_{5/2} and As3d) spectra were recorded on a XPS Microprobe (PHI 5000 Versa
10 Probe II, Physical Electronics) spectrometer at 15 kV using a monochromated AlK_α X-ray source in
11 fixed analyzer transmission mode. The surface morphology of adsorbents was also recorded with a
12 TM3000 (Hitachi) scanning electron microscope (SEM) and their elemental composition was
13 determined with an energy dispersion system (Nano XFlash). SEM images were obtained at a
14 working distance of 7.5 mm and fold magnification of 300x. The elemental composition of each
15 sample was the mean value of two punctual analysis. Textural parameters of selected samples were
16 determined via N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms obtained with a Micromeritics ASAP 2020
17 analyzer. Adsorbent samples loaded with arsenic were also characterized to understand the
18 corresponding adsorption mechanism.
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30 31 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

32 *3.1 Comparison of activation strategies of lanthanum-functionalized adsorbents*

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34 Table 1 shows the arsenic adsorption capacities for the different lanthanum-based adsorbents
35 obtained with N₂ and CO₂ activation. Adsorption capacities of adsorbents activated with CO₂ and N₂
36 ranged from 1.32 to 16.49 mg/g and from 0.89 to 6.31 mg/g, respectively. As a reference point, the
37 arsenic adsorption capacity of the raw char (i.e., without lanthanum functionalization and activation)
38 was 0.35 mg/g, which showed a specific surface area of 31 m²/g with pore diameter of 1.01 nm. It
39 was clear that the lanthanum functionalization significantly improved the arsenic adsorption
40 properties of tested adsorbents independently of the used activation route. Overall, the arsenic
41 adsorption capacities of these materials increased with the lanthanum amount used in the surface
42 functionalization stage. Arsenic removal increased up to 279% for the adsorbents prepared with 10%
43 w/w in comparison with their counterpart synthesized with 5% w/w of lanthanum ratio, see Table 1.
44 These results proved that a major amount of lanthanum utilized for the adsorbent surface
45 functionalization favored the arsenic adsorption due to the incorporation of more functionalities of
46 this multivalent element. Note that the oxygenated functional groups on the char surface contributed
47 to the formation of the lanthanum moieties during adsorbent functionalization and activation as shown
48 in previous studies (Merodio-Morales et al., 2020).
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4 Arsenic adsorption capacities of N-La and C-La adsorbents decreased up to 41 and 77 %,
5 respectively, when the solution pH increased from 7 to 8. The reduction of adsorption capacities at
6 pH 8 was attributed to an increment of the electrostatic repulsion between the arsenic anions (i.e.,
7 HAsO_4^{2-} and H_2AsO_4^-) and surfaces of lanthanum-based adsorbents, which were negatively charged
8 at $\text{pH} > \text{pH}_{\text{pzc}}$ (Tuna et al., 2013). For example, pH_{pzc} of N-La10 and C-La10 were 6.3 and 6.9,
9 respectively, thus indicating that the electrostatic repulsion forces were more significant for the
10 adsorbents activated with N_2 at 800 °C. Therefore, the pH 7 was selected to quantify the kinetics and
11 isotherms of arsenic adsorption. On the other hand, the solution temperature also impacted the arsenic
12 removal with all adsorbents. Arsenic adsorption increased up to 94 and 150% for C-La and N-La
13 samples when temperature changed from 25 to 40 °C. Similar trends have been reported for the
14 arsenic removal with other adsorbents containing lanthanum (Deng et al., 2010; Gupta et al., 2011;
15 Yazdani et al., 2016; Aremu et al., 2019; Lingamdinne et al., 2019; Zeng et al., 2020; Aryal et al.,
16 2022; Carneiro et al., 2022; Sharma et al., 2022; Yin et al., 2022). In summary, the arsenic adsorption
17 capacities of adsorbents activated with CO_2 at room temperature were higher (up to 279%) than those
18 obtained with the samples activated with N_2 at 800 °C. Adsorbents prepared with 10% w/w of
19 lanthanum were also the best samples for the arsenic removal and they were chosen to quantify the
20 corresponding adsorption kinetics and isotherms.
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32 Results from the adsorption kinetic studies with N-La10 and C-La10 samples are reported in
33 Figure 1 including the performance of pseudo-second order model with the parameters given in Table
34 2. The arsenic removal was fast during the first 4 h of operating time and the adsorption equilibrium
35 was reached at ~10 h for tested initial adsorbate concentrations. As expected, the initial arsenic
36 concentration increased the mass transfer thus favoring the adsorption of this geogenic pollutant. The
37 kinetic parameters calculated for the arsenic adsorption on N-La10 and C-La10 are summarized in
38 Table 2. In general, the arsenic adsorption on N-La10 was significantly slower than C-La10. Arsenic
39 adsorption rate constants k_2 calculated with the pseudo-second order model ($R^2 > 0.97$) were $1.5\text{E-}02$
40 – $1.7\text{E-}01$ and $4.0\text{E-}02$ – $5.1\text{E-}02$ g/mg·h for N-La10 and C-La10, respectively. The modeling errors
41 of this adsorption kinetic equation were lower than 0.5%.
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50 Experimental isotherms for the adsorption of arsenic on N-La10 and C-La10 are reported in Figure
51 2 where these isotherms were correlated with the statistical physics models given by Equation (3).
52 These experimental isotherms corresponded to the L-type of Giles classification for liquid adsorption
53 (Giles et al., 1974) that indicated a favorable affinity of this metalloid for the lanthanum-
54 functionalized surface of both adsorbents. Arsenic adsorption capacity was directly proportional to
55 the initial adsorbate concentration in the aqueous solution until the binding sites available for the
56 adsorption were saturated thus achieving the maximum adsorption capacity. Equilibrium adsorption
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4 capacities of N-La10 adsorbent ranged from 2.97 to 5.20, 3.50 to 5.65 and 3.87 to 6.31 mg/g at 25,
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6 30 and 40 °C, respectively, while C-La10 adsorbent showed equilibrium adsorption capacities of 5.09
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8 to 13.71, 5.95 to 15.00 and 6.64 to 16.49 mg/g at the same operating conditions. The maximum
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10 experimental adsorption capacity of C-La10 was 62% higher than that obtained with N-La10
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12 adsorbent thus confirmed that CO₂ activation at room temperature was the best alternative for
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14 tailoring its removal properties. Figure 2 also confirmed that the arsenic adsorption on both adsorbents
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16 was endothermic where the calculated ΔH° was 19 and 38 kJ/mol for N-La10 and C-La10,
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18 respectively. These enthalpy changes can be associated to the presence of both physical and chemical
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20 adsorption forces (like ligand exchange, surface complexation and electrostatic interactions) during
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22 the arsenic removal (Horsfall et al., 2004). However, it could be expected that the interactions of
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24 arsenic anions with C-La10 surface were stronger than those for N-La10 surface. As stated, the
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26 temperature impacted the adsorption process by enhancing the adsorbate diffusion rate through the
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28 boundary layer and inside the adsorbent pore structure (Yazdani et al., 2019)

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30 The monolayer statistical physics model showed $R^2 = 0.95 - 0.98$ for the isotherm data correlation
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32 and its performance is also illustrated in Figure 2. Calculated steric parameters n_{As} and D_{LaX} for the
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34 arsenic adsorption on N-La10 and C-La10 are reported in Table 3. Results showed that the arsenic
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36 adsorption on the surfaces of both adsorbents was a multi-molecular process (i.e., $n_{As} > 1$) especially
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38 at 25 °C where more than one arsenic anion could interact with a lanthanum functionality via an
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40 inclined or perpendicular adsorption position (Amrhar et al., 2021). However, the adsorption
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42 orientation of arsenic anions on adsorbent surfaces changed as the solution temperature increased
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44 where a potential multi-anchorage of this geogenic pollutant could occur at > 30 °C. This result
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46 suggested that arsenic anions were adsorbed on the surfaces of C-La10 and N-La10 with a
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48 combination of both parallel and non-parallel orientations because $n_{As} \in (0.5, 1.0)$ at 30 – 40 °C. Recall
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50 that the dominant binding sites of these adsorbents were the lanthanum-functionalities (Lingamdinne
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52 et al., 2019; Ali et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020; Aryal et al., 2022). The density of lanthanum
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54 functionalities (D_{LaX}) involved in the arsenic adsorption ranged from 0.06 to 0.10 and 0.17 to 0.36
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56 mmol/g for N-La10 and C-La10 samples. The amount of lanthanum functionalities responsible of
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58 arsenic removal increased with temperature for both adsorbents. This behavior was partially related
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60 to the adsorbate diffusion caused by solution temperature (Mahmoodi et al., 2011; Aremu et al.,
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62 2019). In general, the lanthanum functional groups of C-La10 adsorbent were up to three times higher
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64 than those of N-La10 thus confirming that CO₂ activation at low temperature was more effective to
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66 generate binding sites for the arsenic removal. The estimated arsenic adsorption capacities at
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68 saturation ($q_{As,sat}$) were 5.5 – 6.9 mg/g for N-La10 and 15.0 – 19.8 mg/g for C-La10. These saturation
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70 adsorption capacities were close to the experimental values obtained from the isotherms. Calculated

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4 energies (ΔE_{As-LaX}) for the interactions of lanthanum oxygenated functionalities with arsenic anions
5 were 18 – 20 kJ/mol.
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7 The arsenic adsorption capacities of different adsorbents are reported in Table 4. A number of
8 materials showed arsenic adsorption capacities < 10 mg/g. C-La10 adsorbent outperformed several
9 materials including those functionalized with rare earths. But the application of CO₂ activation at
10 room can offer additional advantages to reduce the energy costs associated with the adsorbent
11 preparation and also helps to minimize the corresponding carbon footprint.
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18 *3.2 Surface chemistry of engineered lanthanum-based adsorbents and its impact on the arsenic* 19 *adsorption* 20

21 XRF analysis showed that the N-La10 and C-La10 were mainly composed by an organic matrix
22 (where C and O were the major constituents) and lanthanum, see Table 5. Lanthanum content of C-
23 La10 was slightly higher (~7%) than that of N-La10. A minor proportion of some trace elements (e.g.,
24 Ca, P, K and S) were also identified, which were related to the main mineral constituents of avocado
25 seeds that were employed in the adsorbent preparation (Araújo et al., 2018).
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30 The morphology of N-La10 and C-La10 adsorbents is reported in Figure 3. They showed an
31 irregular, rough and non-porous structure, independently of the activation route. The presence of
32 irregular lanthanum moieties was also detected. These moieties were randomly distributed on the
33 adsorbents surfaces since no apparent agglomeration was observed. After the arsenic adsorption,
34 some morphological changes were observed in the adsorbent samples. In particular, the presence of
35 embedded arsenic crystals forming a large plate-like layered structure was identified. EDX results
36 confirmed that the main elements contained in these adsorbents were carbon (78.64 – 82.54 %),
37 oxygen (9.44 – 18.19 %) and lanthanum (3.46 – 8.02 %). This analysis also showed that the content
38 of rare earth of C-La10 was higher than that of N-La10. The presence of arsenic (2.43 – 4.38 %) was
39 identified in the adsorbent samples obtained from adsorption experiments where the weigh percentage
40 of carbon and lanthanum also decreased. Specific surface area of these adsorbents was low (i.e., < 40
41 m²/g) where the C-La10 sample had a surface area of 29 m²/g with a pore diameter of 1.2 nm.
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50 XRD diffraction patterns of lanthanum-based adsorbents before and after arsenic adsorption are
51 presented in Figure 4. The characteristic broad diffraction peaks of hexagonal graphitic structures at
52 ~ 23 and 43 °2θ were identified in all samples thus indicating the presence of carbon rings disorderly
53 stacked up associated to the carbon-based amorphous structure of adsorbents (Kumar and Jena, 2015;
54 Hidayu et al., 2016; González-García et al., 2018). Lanthanum carbonate hydroxide (ICDD: 00-049-
55 0981) and lanthanum hydroxide (ICDD: 01-083-2034) phases were identified in the diffraction
56 patters of C-La10 and N-La10 adsorbents, where the first one is the main phase (~80%). The
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4 formation of these lanthanum species can be explained considering the chemistry of this rare earth
5 and the possible reactions that could occur during the surface functionalization and activation of these
6 adsorbents. First, the precipitation of lanthanum hydroxide for the functionalization of carbon-based
7 adsorbent followed the next reaction
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10 This reaction caused that lanthanum-oxygenated functionalities were generated on the adsorbent
11 surface. For the case of adsorbent activation with CO_2 at room temperature, a partial carbonation of
12 lanthanum-oxygenated functionalities occurred. According to the literature (Isahak et al., 2015), the
13 carbonation of lanthanum hydroxide can be performed at low temperature according to the next
14 reaction
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16 Previous studies have proved that materials containing lanthanum oxides can be used for the CO_2
17 capture at $< 60^\circ\text{C}$ where physical interaction forces could be involved thus being a reversible process
18 (Hammami et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2015; Gong et al., 2018). These antecedents explained the
19 identification of crystalline structures related to both lanthanum carbonate hydroxide and lanthanum
20 hydroxide in the C-La10 sample.
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22 On the other hand, the formation of lanthanum oxygenated functionalities on N-La10 surface (i.e.,
23 adsorbent activated with N_2 at 800°C) could result from a series of intermediate reactions that were
24 temperature dependent. Specifically, it has been documented that the carbonation of lanthanum
25 hydroxide can occur via the next reactions
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27 At $\sim 320^\circ\text{C}$, the dehydration of lanthanum hydroxide can take place leading to the formation of
28 lanthanum oxyhydroxide (LaOOH), which can remain stable up to 400°C (Deng et al., 2003; Samata
29 et al., 2007; Meng et al., 2019). LaOOH can turn into La_2O_3 at around 500°C (Neumann and Walter,
30 2006; Yang et al., 2019), which can be transformed to lanthanum oxide carbonate at $\sim 650^\circ\text{C}$ in the
31 presence of CO_2 (Orera et al., 2013; Jiang et al., 2020). This carbonate phase is stable until $\sim 950^\circ\text{C}$
32 (Pons et al., 2014). But, its exposure to ambient atmosphere can generate the lanthanum carbonate
33 hydroxide (Bakiz et al., 2010). The formation of lanthanum compounds on the carbon-based
34 adsorbent is illustrated in Figure 5. During the adsorbent activation at 800°C for 2 h with N_2 flow,
35 CO_2 and H_2O released from the partial thermal degradation of oxygenated functionalities from
36 adsorbent structure contributed to the partial carbonation of its lanthanum oxygenated functionalities.
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4 Also, the formation of these lanthanum functional groups could be achieved, in a minor extent, during
5 the phase deposition (which was performed under atmospheric air) and the content of carbonates in
6 NaOH solution used in the adsorbent preparation. By this reason, lanthanum hydroxide and
7 lanthanum carbonate hydroxide were also identified in the diffraction pattern of N-La10 sample.
8 However, the formation of these crystalline structures was favored when N₂ activation was employed
9 instead CO₂ activation, which can be supported by the better crystallinity observed from XRD pattern
10 of N-La10 sample, see Figure 4. In both cases, the lanthanum can act as a CO₂ reservoir, which is
11 adsorbed as a carbonate specie (Garbarino et al., 2019). CO₂ can interact with lanthanum moieties by
12 forming La-O bonds and, depending on the lanthanum-type group, the interaction is via physisorption
13 (i.e., with hydroxyl groups) or chemisorption (i.e., with oxygen vacancy) (Hammami et al., 2009;
14 Guo et al., 2022). After the arsenic adsorption, the crystalline structure of both adsorbents changed,
15 see Figure 4b. A reduction in the peak intensity was observed and the crystalline phase of arsenic
16 oxide (ICDD: 01-071-1694) was detected, thus confirming that the arsenic adsorption occurred. Note
17 that the XRD peaks of lanthanum carbonate hydroxide were not identified in the adsorbent samples
18 loaded with arsenic.

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29 FTIR results of N-La10 and C-La10 adsorbents with and without loaded arsenic are reported in
30 Figure 6. These spectra contained three main regions comprising the vibrational frequencies between
31 ~3650 to 2800, ~1850 to 850 and below 700 cm⁻¹, respectively. The strong and wide absorption band
32 at ~3440 cm⁻¹ was ascribed to O-H stretching vibration of hydroxyl groups associated to hydrogen-
33 bonded interlayer water molecules and structural hydroxyl groups (Levan et al., 1993; Guo et al.,
34 2012; Wang et al., 2013; Li et al., 2020). The absorption bands at ~1620, 1460 and 1400 cm⁻¹ were
35 attributed to C-O and CO= stretching vibrations of carbonate group (Wang et al., 2013; Huo et al.,
36 2020). Specifically, the absorption bands between ~1500 and 1400 cm⁻¹ arose from the ν_3 asymmetric
37 stretching vibration of carbonate (Levan et al., 1993; Wang et al., 2013; Stoyanova et al., 2019). The
38 ν_1 (symmetric), ν_2 (out-of-plane bending) and ν_4 (in-plane bending) vibrations of carbonate group were
39 also observed via the bands located at ~1040, 850 and 730 cm⁻¹, respectively (Levan et al., 1993;
40 Wang et al., 2013). The bending vibration of La-OH groups were related to the absorption bands at
41 ~1140 and 1115 cm⁻¹ (Li et al., 2020). The absorption bands below 700 cm⁻¹ were attributed to lattice
42 vibration modes of La-O and La-OH (Guo et al., 2012). FTIR spectra also confirmed that C-La10
43 contained more lanthanum oxygenated functionalities than N-La10.

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FTIR spectra of adsorbent samples obtained after arsenic removal indicated that the band at ~3440
cm⁻¹ was considerably reduced, and the bands of carbonate groups located between 1500 and 1400
cm⁻¹ disappeared leading to the formation of a new intense and sharp absorption band at ~1380 cm⁻¹
that could be assigned to As-O bond (Shi et al., 2015). The bending vibration bands at ~1140 and

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4 1115 cm⁻¹ also gone and a new vibration band at ~880 cm⁻¹ was detected and attributed to As-O-La
5 bonds (Sawana et al., 2017). For illustration, the results of XPS analysis of N-La10 adsorbent sample
6 is reported in Figure 7. XPS survey scan spectrum showed the presence of carbon, oxygen and
7 lanthanum as the main elements of this material, while the sample obtained from adsorption
8 experiments indicated additionally arsenic (Figure 7b).

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14 These characterization results suggested that lanthanum oxygenated functionalities participated in
15 the arsenic adsorption via a ligand exchange and/or surface complexation interactions (Lingamdinne
16 et al., 2019; Rios-Saldaña et al., 2022). Similar adsorption interactions have been proposed for the
17 arsenic adsorption with adsorbents functionalized with multivalent species including rare earths (Zhu
18 et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2014; Lingamdinne et al., 2019; Rios-Saldaña et al., 2022). In particular, the
19 ligand exchange for C-La10 and N-La10 implied the decarbonation of their lanthanum oxygenated
20 functional groups in the aqueous solution to allow the attachment of the arsenic anions on the
21 adsorbent surface. The increment of solution temperature favored this decarbonation process and,
22 consequently, the amount of lanthanum oxygenated functionalities available for arsenic removal also
23 increased. This phenomenon can explain the endothermic arsenic adsorption behavior of both
24 adsorbents. In this direction, Guo et al. (2012) have stated that the adsorption of arsenic anions via
25 the decarbonation of lanthanum oxygenated functionalities was feasible. Based on these findings, the
26 possible adsorption mechanism could be represented as follows (Tokunaga et al., 1997)

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The interesting surface chemistry of this lanthanum-functionalized adsorbent can allow the
diversification of its applications in environmental protection. In particular, the char functionalized
with lanthanum via the precipitation method can be directly used in CO₂ sequestration from
atmosphere with the aim of achieving the carbonation of their lanthanum functionalities (i.e., its
activation at low temperature). After that, this final adsorbent can be employed in the adsorption of
arsenic from groundwater. This approach could contribute to maximize the application and
exploitation of this adsorbent as a multifunctional material for facing environmental pollution in both
water and air, and to reduce its production cost since atmospheric CO₂ could be utilized during the
adsorbent functionalization and activation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study has introduced a new activation route using carbon dioxide at room temperature to
tailor the arsenic adsorption properties of a carbon-based adsorbent functionalized with lanthanum.
Results showed that the carbonation of lanthanum oxygenated functionalities of the adsorbent
contributed to improve its arsenic adsorption capacities in comparison with an activation performed

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4 at 800 °C under N₂ atmosphere. This engineered lanthanum-based adsorbent showed adsorption
5 capacities up to 19.8 mg/g at 40 °C and pH 7 thus outperforming other adsorbents reported in the
6 literature. The adsorption mechanism of arsenic on this engineered adsorbent implied ligand exchange
7 and surface complexation reactions where the lanthanum oxygenated functionalities played a relevant
8 role. The endothermic nature of arsenic adsorption on the engineered lanthanum-based adsorbent was
9 associated to the decarbonation of its lanthanum oxygenated functionalities in the aqueous solution.
10 The adsorption mechanism of this geogenic pollutant transited from a multi-molecular process at 25
11 °C to a multi-anchorage process at > 30 °C. CO₂ activation at room temperature is an attractive
12 strategy that could reduce the energy consumption and production costs of adsorbents for the
13 treatment of groundwater polluted by arsenic. Results of this study can be also extended to
14 functionalize other carbon-based adsorbents using lanthanum to improve their arsenic adsorption
15 properties for groundwater purification. Finally, this engineered lanthanum-based adsorbent can be
16 multifunctional where CO₂ sequestration and groundwater depollution can be performed in a
17 sequential effective approach.
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30
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44 Figure 1. Kinetics for the arsenic adsorption from aqueous solution using N-La10 and C-La10
45 adsorbents at pH 7 and 30 °C. Initial arsenic concentration: 50 (●), 100 (▲) and 200 (■) mg/L. The
46 parameters of pseudo-second-order model are given in Table 2.
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Figure 2. Isotherms of arsenic adsorption from aqueous solution using N-La10 and C-La10 at pH 7. Solution temperature, °C: (●) 25, (▲) 30 and (■) 40. The parameters of the statistical physics model are given in Table 3.

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Figure 3. SEM micrographs (300x) of lanthanum-based adsorbents used in the arsenic adsorption.

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Figure 4. X-ray diffraction patterns of N-La10 and C-La10 a) before and b) after arsenic adsorption.

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Figure 5. Schematic representation of the surface chemistry functionalization of the adsorbents using CO_2 and N_2 activation.

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Figure 6. FTIR spectra of N-La10 and C-La10 adsorbents a) before and b) after arsenic adsorption.

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Figure 7. Survey and deconvolution of XPS spectra of oxygen, lanthanum and arsenic for N-La10 sample a) before and b) after the arsenic adsorption.

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12 Table 1. Arsenic adsorption capacities of carbon-based adsorbents functionalized with lanthanum and
13 activated with CO₂ (C-La) and N₂ (N-La).
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<i>Adsorbent</i>	<i>pH</i>	<i>Adsorption capacities (mg/g) for</i>		
		25 °C	30 °C	40 °C
C-La5	7	1.9	2.7	3.8
	8	1.3	2.0	2.6
C-La10	7	13.7	15.0	16.5
	8	3.5	3.8	3.9
N-La5	7	1.1	2.1	2.6
	8	0.9	1.4	1.7
N-La10	7	4.9	5.6	6.3
	8	3.0	3.2	3.7

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38 Table 2. Calculated kinetic parameters for the arsenic adsorption on N-La10 and C-La10 at pH 7 and
39 30 °C.
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<i>Adsorbent</i>	<i>C_{As,ini}</i>	<i>q_{As,eq}, mg/g</i>	<i>k₂, g/mg-h</i>	<i>R²</i>	<i>Modeling error, %</i>
N-La10	50	6.9	1.5E-02	0.981	0.32 ± 0.22
	100	7.4	2.3E-02	0.978	0.34 ± 0.28
	200	6.3	1.7E-01	0.974	0.23 ± 0.30
C-La10	50	14.5	4.0E-02	0.992	0.28 ± 0.26
	100	14.6	5.1E-02	0.988	0.35 ± 0.25
	200	16.5	4.0E-02	0.987	0.40 ± 0.36

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Table 3. Calculated statistical physics parameters for the arsenic adsorption on N-La10 and C-La10 at pH 7 and 25 – 40 °C.

<i>Adsorbent</i>	<i>Temperature, °C</i>	n_{As}	D_{LaX} , mmol/g	q_{As} , mg/g
N-La10	25	1.2	0.06	5.5
	30	1.1	0.07	6.0
	40	0.9	0.10	6.9
C-La10	25	1.2	0.17	15.0
	30	1.0	0.23	16.7
	40	0.7	0.36	19.8

Table 4. Arsenic adsorption capacities (q_{max}) of different adsorbents reported in literature.

Adsorbent	Experimental conditions		q_{max} , mg/g	Reference
	pH	Temperature, °C		
Activated carbon from oat hulls	5	30	~ 2.7	Chuang et al. (2005)
Cerium-exchanged zeolite	4	25	8.7	Haron et al. (2008)
Ce-Ti oxide adsorbent	6	25	45.0	Deng et al. (2010)
Magnetite nanoparticles	2	30	~ 3.7	Chowdhury and Yanful (2011)
Ceria associated manganese oxide nanoparticles	7	30	18.7	Gupta et al. (2011)
Cerium loaded resins	6	25	~ 3.5	He et al. (2012)
Cerium oxide nanoparticles	7	25	~ 100.0	Li et al. (2012)
Iron (oxy-hydr)oxides apricot stone based activated carbon	3	25	~ 4.5	Tuna et al. (2013)
Titanium-coated carbon nanotubes	7	25	2.3	Liu et al. (2014)
Iron impregnated biochar	5.8	20	2.2	Hu et al. (2015)
Iron-enriched aluminosilicate fly ash	6	27	0.6	Meher et al. (2015)
Iron modified fly ash	2.3	25	1.2	Zhang et al. (2016)
Ceria modified activated carbon	---	---	~ 10.3	Sawana et al. (2017)
Cerium oxide modified activated carbon	5	25	~ 40.0	Yu et al. (2017)
Cerium-based magnetic adsorbents	9	25	~ 26.0	Feng et al. (2018)
Iron oxide activated carbon composite	8	25	6.7	Joshi et al. (2019)
Graphene oxide-lanthanum fluoride nanocomposite	6	---	18.5	Lingamdinne et al. (2019)
Almond shell biochar	7.2	20	4.9	Ali et al. (2020)
Ceria-incorporated zirconia nanocomposites	5	30	17.1	Ghosh et al. (2020)
Lanthanum immobilized electrospun chitosan nanofiber	6	---	~ 75.0	Tan et al. (2020)
Lignin-based biochar decorated with zinc	6	---	18.3	Park et al. (2021)
Lanthanum saponified watermelon rind	12.08	35	58.1	Aryal et al. (2022)

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Table 5. XRF results for the best lanthanum-based adsorbents obtained from N₂ and CO₂ activation.

Elemental composition, %	Adsorbent	
	N-La10	C-La10
CH*	89.82	89.08
P	0.45	0.37
Ca	0.46	0.48
S	0.11	0.08
K	0.06	0.22
La	8.74	9.36
Others	0.36	0.41

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: